

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR FOR POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH BENZOYLATED SUGARCANE FIBERS

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Keywords: *Polypropylene (PP), Sugarcane bagasse fibers, Mechanical properties, Statistical analysis.*

1 Introduction

Sugarcane bagasse is an abundant agro-industrial by product in Brazil. Although it is used in many different applications [1], the world still produces an excess of approximately 54 million tons annually. This agricultural material therefore represents an abundant, inexpensive, and readily available source of renewable lignocellulosic biomass [2]. Sugarcane straw fiber is also a readily available lignocellulosic material due to the recent mechanization of harvesting, and is now being evaluated. The estimated annual world supply of sugarcane straw is approximately 30 million tons [3].

The search in turn of new alternatives for materials that offer advantages to the environment has led to growing research on the application on natural fibers as reinforcement of polymers, mainly due to their high stiffness, low density and because the fibers are also highly favorable from the standpoint of the modulus when compared to other polymeric materials.

In addition to these characteristics, natural fibers have other advantages, such as biodegradability, low cost, low abrasiveness, ease in processing, recyclability and low power consumption during preparation [4 - 8]. In addition, the natural fibers are derived from renewable resources; they are available in large quantities, contributing even further to the rising interest in studying these materials. The use of natural fibers in composites presents some disadvantages, such as high moisture absorption,

low decomposition temperature and poor adhesion between the fiber and matrix. Despite these drawbacks, the use of these fibers in composites has been growing due to the possibility of circumventing these problems [4].

Polypropylene is a semicrystalline polymer obtained by polyaddition, and it is widely used as a thermoplastic in engineering applications. The addition of fibers in polymer matrices, such as polypropylene is known to modify the mechanical properties of the resulting composite [9].

The use of lignocellulosic fibers and its components as raw material in the composites has been considered as a technological progress in the context of sustainable development [5].

Composite materials have received a crescent attention, particularly in regard to applications in industry segments, e.g. automotive and furniture [5]. The main problem with fiber/ matrix composites is related to the absence of interfacial interaction between the hydrophobic matrix and the hydrophilic fibers. The hydroxyl groups, which contribute greatly to the hygroscopicity of the materials, are attached to cellulose, lignin and hemicellulose and can be chemically modified to possess hydrophobic properties. Thus, we applied chemical surface treatments to reduce the hydrophilic nature of the fibers, making them more compatible with hydrophobic (PP) matrix. Many methods for fiber surface modifications, such as mercerization, latex

coating, gamma irradiation, silane treatment, isocyanate treatment, acetylation and peroxide treatment, have been tested as methods to reduce the hydrophilicity and decrease water absorption [5, 9, 10].

In this work, we use the chemical modifications by esterification with benzoyl chloride. This chemical modification has accompanied with a pretreatment in aqueous NaOH to activate the hydroxyl groups, transforming them into alkoxides, and facilitating the subsequent reaction with benzoyl chloride and also increasing the accessibility of the reagent to the interior of the fibers [11, 12].

Thus, the insertion of aromatic rings in the fiber's chemical structure may promote best interaction between the fiber and the matrix. In this case, the benzoyl groups, similar to that of lignin, promote the compatibility with non-polar structure of PP [5, 9, 10]. A possible reaction scheme for benzoylation is described in Figure 1.

The structure of the group (benzoyl) that was inserted in the fiber structure is similar to the structure of lignin, which is found in lignocellulosic materials. The main components in the structure of lignocellulosic materials are cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin [9, 10].

Figure 1. Reaction scheme of natural fibers with benzoyl chloride.

Lignin is the major non-carbohydrate found in plant cell walls. Chemically, it is different from cellulose and hemicellulose, and it is more difficult. It has cross-connections and a three-dimensional macromolecular structure formed from phenolic units. The aromatic nature of the phenolic units gives lignin its apolar and hydrophobic characteristics [10].

Therefore, the mechanical behavior of composites reinforced with fibers shows that these materials can perform structural and non-structural applications. The synergetic characteristics of composite materials depend on the initial characteristics of the reinforcement or the matrix [9].

In this work, polypropylene was used as the matrix, and as reinforcement non-modified and modified sugarcane bagasse fiber. This work describes an

investigation of mechanical behavior of polypropylene composites reinforced with benzoylated sugarcane bagasse fibers. The insertion of high modulus natural fibers in thermoplastic polymer matrices (low modulus) can contribute to the obtainment of materials with remarkable properties.

The modulus of elasticity in tension and bending are directly influenced by the high modulus of the fibers [11]. Gassan; Bledzki (1997) [13] found that the flexural strength of jute/ polypropylene composites increases when the amount of fibers grows. The method of experiment factorial planning was also used. And then, scanning electron microscopy was employed to evaluate the morphological aspects of the fibers after the modification process [5].

2 Experimental

2.1 Chemical modification of sugarcane fibers by benzoylation

Two grams of lignocellulosic material were added to a 50 mL Becker flask and mixed with 20 mL of aqueous NaOH (18% w/v). After 2 hours, aqueous NaOH (10% w/v) and distilled water (total of 50 mL) were added. The mixture was then transferred to a 500-mL round flask with the introduction of 10 mL of benzoyl chloride. The temperature was raised to 55°C, and the reaction proceeded for 1 to 5 hours.

2.2 Composite Preparation, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The composites were prepared in batches of 50 g in a thermokinetic mixer (model MH - 50H) rotating at 5250 rpm with fiber fractions of either 10, 15 or 20% by weight (% wt) / PP. Morphological analysis of modified fibers was performed using a JEOL JSM - 7001F instrument (SEM). The fiber surfaces were coated with gold and then imaged using the SEM operated at 20 keV.

2.3 Characterization of modified materials by FTIR

Samples of modified materials were analyzed using FTIR spectroscopy. The samples (2 mg) were ground with KBr (200 mg) and formed into pellets. The spectra were recorded with a Perkin Elmer

Spectrometer (Spectrum One) in the 400 - 4000 cm^{-1} range, using 16 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

2.4 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

TGA were carried out using a Perkin Elmer (TGA 7) instrument, in a N_2 atmosphere, from 30 to 650°C with a 10°C.min⁻¹ heating rate.

2.5 Mechanical Tests

For all standard tests, composites were analyzed in an “Instron” universal-testing machine (model 4301), equipped with pneumatic claws. In the tensile tests, five specimens of composites were analyzed, with dimensions in agreement with the ASTM D 638 [14]. In the flexural tests, five specimens were analyzed with dimensions in agreement with the ASTM D 790 standard [15].

2.6 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses of different composites, considering fiber content and treatment of fibers were performed. Tensile strength (MOR_t) and flexural strength (MOR_f) analysis was performed, leading to a full factorial design type 2¹4¹, generating eight experimental conditions (EC), laid out in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental conditions (EC) in terms of fiber content and treatment.

EC	Treatment	Fiber Fraction (% wt)
C1	non-modified	0
C2	non-modified	10
C3	non-modified	15
C4	non-modified	20
C5	Benzoylated	0
C6	Benzoylated	10
C7	Benzoylated	15
C8	Benzoylated	20

Analysis of variance was employed to verify the effect of the treatment on the fibers, the fiber content, and the interaction between them on the investigated mechanical properties [16].

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Chemical modification of sugarcane fibers by benzoylation

As mentioned previously, the procedures of surface modification were applied to sugarcane bagasse. About the benzoylation treatment, it is observed a consistent weight gain as a function of time, as shows in the Table 2.

Table 2: Variation of weight as a function of reaction time.

Reaction time (h)	Variation of weight (%)
Branco (4h)	-47.5
1	-1.4
3	-1.5
4	4.6
5	2.0

It is interesting to note that from 1 h reaction with benzoyl chloride was observed a slight weight variations (loss of 1.5% to 4.6%). This small change in all the reaction time, it can be related to the benzoylation prevent hydrolysis of the cellulose, leaving the cellulose fibers better preserved.

It is possible to estimate that there was incorporated group benzoylated on the cellulose structure. For the experiments in 4 h, the blank presented a weight loss of 47.5% and for benzoylated materials and an increase of weight of 4.6% resulting in an total increase in weight (relative to blank) 120.2%. Thus, it is possible the incorporation of up to two groups per benzoylated cellulose glucose unit.

3.2 Composite Preparation, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

A solubilization in part of the lignin was also observed. The treatment effectiveness was evaluated by SEM, and the Figure 2 shows the morphological aspects of the fibers. SEM characterization revealed that the chemical treatment changed the morphology of the fibers.

The *in nature* and modified fibers showed distinctions, as the presence of pits (bagasse) and plasticization (benzoylation) caused by fiber degradation. There was a decrease in lignin, hemicellulose and extractives content after treatment, improving the compatibility between the fibers and the matrix [6]. The chemical modification of the fibers was confirmed through SEM. That is,

this treatment causes changes to the surface structure of the fiber.

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of sugarcane (A, B) *in natura* bagasse fibers and (C, D) benzoylated fibers.

After the chemical modification, the polypropylene (PP) composites reinforced with 10, 15 or 20% by weight of non-modified and benzoylated sugarcane bagasse fibers were obtained throughout a thermokinetic mixer turning at high speeds to process fiber and PP batches.

The mixing between the polymer matrix and the fiber is promoted by PP melting, due to the heating of the system. Mixing time production for the fiber and the PP matrix varied according to fiber type and content. It was observed that the mixing time for preparation of composites with 10% by weight of fibers reaches to 200 s and for 20% by weight, 750 s. The increased mixing time creates a greater amount of fibers because of the longer fiber/ fiber contact. Hence, the matrix does not easily enter into direct contact with the wall of the bipartite capsule. This causes the fusion of the matrix and subsequent incorporation of the fiber. Furthermore, long mixing times may cause excessive breakdown and thermal degradation of fibers, which will negatively affect the composite properties [4, 5].

3.3 Characterization of modified materials by FTIR

Products resulting from the benzoylation reactions were analyzed using an FTIR spectrometer. The lignocellulosic materials, in the form of bagasse pulps and *in natura* bagasse were modified separately for different reactions times and each obtained product was analyzed. During the chemical modification of bagasse, there may have been a concurrent reaction between lignin and hemicellulose with cellulose, due to presence of OH groups.

Benzoylated pulps that contain approximately 80% cellulose provide the best medium to investigate the chemical modification. Fig. 3 compares the FTIR spectra of bagasse pulp modified by benzoylation to those of non-modified bagasse pulp. The insertion of benzoyl groups in the cellulose structure through the esterification reaction can cause further changes in the absorption properties in the infrared region. We observed decreases in OH band intensity (3400 cm^{-1}), typical of intermolecular hydrogen bonds (large strip of C-H stretching of cellulose - 2900 cm^{-1}). In C, we observe the appearance of a carbonyl band from ester. D and E delimit the in-plane angular deformation of carbonyl band from $1100 - 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. At a wavenumber of 718 cm^{-1} (F), a band appeared, attributed to a mono-substituted aromatic ring.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectra ($400 - 4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of pulps: --- control; --- benzoylated bagasse pulp.

3.4 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The modified materials and the respective controls were analyzed by thermogravimetric (TG) analysis. TG analysis was used to evaluate the thermal stability of the samples. Fig. 4 shows the curve behavior of thermal degradation on derivatives, compared to the control. The curves show that the materials without chemical modification present a higher initial weight loss than the derivatives.

Fig. 4. Curves behavior of thermal degradation of bagasse pulps modified by benzoylation in comparison to non-modified pulps.

Table 3 shows the percentage of weight loss between 100 and 500°C, as well as the degradation peak temperatures calculated from the digital data of TG. The weight loss of modified materials after 400°C was higher than that of the non-modified materials. This suggests that the chemical modification of the fibers result in structures that are less stable at high temperatures.

Table 3. Weight loss at different temperatures and temperatures of degradation peaks temperatures of several materials from chemical modification of pulps.

Samples	Weight loss (%)				Degradation temperature s (°C)*
	100 °C	200 °C	400 °C	500 °C	
Benzoylated bagasse pulp	3.2	3.8	90.8	92.1	45.3 361.5
Bagasse pulp	3.1	5.3	71.3	75.4	56.3 324.4

*Sets obtained by DTG curves; ¹ materials modified after 4 h reaction; ² control of chemical modification (5 h reaction).

The weight loss behavior for benzoylated bagasse pulp was similar to non-modified materials at 200°C.

Between 400 and 500°C, however, the weight loss was more accentuated for modified pulps, reaching 98.7%. Nevertheless, the benzoylated bagasse pulp had a higher degradation temperature (361.5°C) than the other analyzed materials did.

3.5 Mechanical Tests

Various composite systems were obtained, as described in Table 4, using polypropylene as matrix and both *in nature* and chemically modified fibers as reinforcements.

Table 4. Mechanical results for tensile and flexural properties for PP composites reinforced with non-modified and benzoylated fibers.

Reinforcement (% wt)	Tensile Strength (MPa)		Flexural Strength (MPa)	
	BN*	BB**	BN*	BB**
0	26.9 ± 1.3	26.9 ± 1.3	25.4 ± 0.1	25.4 ± 0.1
10	26.3 ± 0.2	28.6 ± 0.3	30.9 ± 0.1	29.8 ± 0.0
15	23.8 ± 0.5	26.9 ± 0.3	31.3 ± 0.4	30.7 ± 0.2
20	24.8 ± 0.2	27.1 ± 1.1	35.1 ± 1.2	31.3 ± 0.2

* BN (bagasse *in nature*); ** BB (benzoylated bagasse).

Table 4 shows that the composites containing benzoylated fibers could be adhering more to the polymer because of the presence of the polar groups (benzoyl), which increases the values for tensile strength.

Thus, the values for tensile strength increased from 8.7% for 10 wt%, 13% for 15 wt% and 9.3% for 20 wt% for benzoylated fibers when compared to the non-modified fibers. Flexural strength, on the other hand, is impaired in the composites reinforced with benzoylated fibers, although the rigidity of the material leads to the rupture of all BB composites independent of the composition. Something that was not observed for any composite reinforced with *in nature* sugarcane bagasse.

3.6 Statistical Analysis

Table 5 shows the results for the mechanical properties of the eight investigated experimental conditions.

Table 5. Mechanical properties from tensile and flexural tests for neat PP and composites reinforced with BB.

EC	MOR _t (MPa)	MOR _f (MPa)
C1	26.9 ± 1.3	25.4 ± 0.1
C2	26.3 ± 0.2	30.9 ± 0.1
C3	23.8 ± 0.5	31.3 ± 0.4
C4	24.8 ± 0.2	35.1 ± 1.2
C5	26.9 ± 1.3	25.4 ± 0.1
C6	28.6 ± 0.3	29.8 ± 0.0
C7	26.9 ± 0.3	30.7 ± 0.2
C8	27.1 ± 1.1	31.3 ± 0.2

Where (MOR_t): tensile strength and (MOR_f): flexural strength.

Table 6 shows the analysis of variance of the eight conditions of the full factorial design on the investigated mechanical properties. Underlined are the P-values less than or equal to 0.05 (5%), which indicate significance up to 95 % [12]. These values are presented in conjunction with their corresponding R² coefficients of determination.

Table 6. Analysis of variance in terms of fiber content and treatment.

Treatment/Fiber	MOR _t (MPa)		MOR _f (MPa)	
	P-value	R ²	P-value	R ²
Treatment	0.405	77%	<u>0.002</u>	86%
Fiber fraction	0.064	73%	0.200	81%
Treatment × Fiber fraction	0.154	83%	0.256	75%

In analysis of variance both samples are assumed to be extracted from independent populations, which can be described by a normal distribution [12]. The Anderson-Darling normality test was therefore employed and the normal distribution of the investigated responses was established with all P-values being greater than 0.05 and falling in the interval between 0.127 and 0.604.

The factors investigated in Table 5, treatment was the only one considered remarkable, showing a P-value less than 0.05 for the flexural strength modulus. This implies that treatment, fiber content and their interaction produced comparable results in almost all investigated responses. Figure 2 shows the interaction between the factors for the investigated responses.

The introduction of non-modified fibers (*in nature*) caused a decrease in the strength of composites when compared to the results of the material produced from 100% polypropylene (Figure 5a).

Figure 5. Interaction between factors (non-modified and benzoylated fibers).

The lowest values were found for the materials consisting of 15 % wt fibers (C3), which were 11.52% worse than the condition of the reference materials (C1). With the addition of 0% to 10 % wt

of fibers, the reduction in tensile strength was 2.23%. With 10% to 15 %wt of fibers, tensile strength was reduced by 9.51%. And with 15% to 20 %wt of fibers, the strength of composites increased by 4.20%. Treating the bagasse fibers provided excellent results for the tensile strength of all composites when compared with materials that did not receive benzylation treatment (Figure 5). The addition of 10 %wt of bagasse fibers caused the tensile strength of materials to increase by 6.32%. When 10% to 15 %wt was added, the tensile strength was reduced by 5.94%. And it increased by 0.74% for a 15% to 20 % wt percentage of fibers. The progressive increase of the fraction of *in nature* and treated fibers led to successive increases in the flexural strength of the composites (Figure 5b). The highest values were observed for condition C4, which was 38.19% superior in this regard when compared to materials made from 100% polypropylene (C1). For all investigated composites, the treatment of the fibers yielded lower values for flexural strength when compared to the untreated conditions. The largest difference was obtained for the composite with 20 %wt of fibers, with the composites with non-modified fibers having 12.14% superior results in comparison to those made with treated fibers.

4 Conclusions

During the benzylation reaction of bagasse, it was observed a constant weight gain as a function of time. The chemical modification was necessary to reduce the hydrophilicity of the fibers and to increase the interfacial adhesion of polar fibers with the apolar matrix. SEM allowed us to evaluate the morphology and dimensions of the modified and unmodified fibers and indicated that there were considerable morphology changes after the chemical treatments. Spectra from FTIR confirmed that esterification reactions had taken place. The newly added groups resulted in decreases in the OH bands and the appearance of aromatic groups. Thermal analysis revealed that the lignocellulosic material without modification has a higher thermal stability than the modified fibers at low temperatures. The benzyolated fibers insertion caused an increase in the tensile strength in regard to non-modified fibers. However for flexural strength, the chemical modification decreased this mechanical property. Already, the flexural modulus values increase when

compared to neat PP (15 and 20 % by weight of fibers). Among the employed experimental factors, treatment of the fibers proved to be the most significant, directly affecting the flexural strength of the composites, indicating that the compositions of the fibers and the interaction between the two factors had little influence on the evaluated mechanical properties. The results for strength obtained from the uniaxial tensile tests demonstrated the effectiveness of treating the fibers with benzoyl groups, with condition C6 providing the best results, followed by condition C7. The progressive use of sugarcane bagasse fibers provided successive increases in flexural strength of the composites for both treatments and the composites with the four non-modified fibers yielded the best results. This indicates that, when flexural strength was concerned, treatment was ineffective. In general, the treatment produced higher values for the material in two of the three investigated fiber composites and proved to be efficient in this regard.

5 Acknowledgements

To REUNI/ CAPES, who provided a master scholarship for the first author and FINATEC and DPP/ UnB for the financial support of this project.

6 References

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